

Case Report

Acute Carbamazepine Toxicity Triggered by Paxlovid: A Stroke Mimic in a Patient With Epilepsy

Parjanya Shah MD¹, Inban Pugazhendi MD¹, Nikhila Chelikam MD MSCR¹, Saloni Brahmhatt MD¹

¹NYMC at Saint Mary's and Saint Clare's Internal Medicine Residency Program, Denville, NJ, USA

Background:

Carbamazepine (CBZ) is an antiseizure medication with a narrow therapeutic index and is primarily metabolized by CYP3A4. Ritonavir, co-formulated with nirmatrelvir in Paxlovid, is a potent CYP3A4 inhibitor and can markedly raise CBZ concentrations. Although this interaction is pharmacologically well recognized, contemporary cases in the COVID-19 era remain uncommon.

Case Presentation:

A 52-year-old man with a seizure disorder on chronic CBZ and valproate presented with acute dysarthria, ataxia, lethargy, and nausea two days after starting Paxlovid.

Keywords: Carbamazepine, Nirmatrelvir/ritonavir, Drug–drug interaction, CYP3A4 inhibition, Antiseizure medications

Stroke alert evaluation and CT/CTA were negative. His CBZ level was markedly elevated at 19.8 µg/mL. Paxlovid and CBZ were discontinued, supportive care was provided, and his neurologic symptoms resolved as CBZ levels declined.

Conclusion:

This case highlights a serious drug–drug interaction in which ritonavir inhibited CBZ metabolism, resulting in acute neurotoxicity mimicking stroke. Clinicians should avoid co-prescribing Paxlovid with CBZ and should monitor antiseizure drug levels when initiating or discontinuing ritonavir-containing regimens.

Introduction

Carbamazepine (CBZ) is a widely used antiseizure medication for epilepsy, trigeminal neuralgia, and bipolar disorder. It undergoes hepatic metabolism primarily through cytochrome P450 3A4 (CYP3A4), making serum concentrations highly sensitive to changes in CYP3A4 activity (1). Because CBZ has a narrow therapeutic index, inhibition of CYP3A4 can rapidly increase drug levels and precipitate toxicity.

Ritonavir, developed initially as an HIV protease inhibitor, is widely used as a pharmacokinetic enhancer due to its potent mechanism-based inhibition of CYP3A4 (2). CBZ levels are typically therapeutic at 4–12 µg/mL, with toxicity commonly emerging above 12–15 µg/mL (3).

The interaction between CBZ and ritonavir has been recognized for decades: early reports described acute CBZ toxicity presenting with vertigo, lethargy, gait instability, and hepatotoxicity shortly after ritonavir initiation (4–8). With the introduction of Paxlovid during the COVID-19 pandemic, these concerns resurfaced.

Current guidelines advise avoiding coadministration due to both the risk of CBZ toxicity and the possibility of reduced antiviral efficacy (2,9).

We present a case of acute CBZ toxicity triggered by Paxlovid, mimicking an acute cerebrovascular event.

Case Presentation

A 52-year-old man with a history of seizure disorder status post craniotomy approximately 35 years earlier presented to the emergency department after his mother noticed new-onset slurred speech, tremors, unsteady gait, lethargy, and nausea. He had tested positive for COVID-19 two days earlier and began Paxlovid shortly thereafter. His chronic antiseizure regimen included carbamazepine 600 mg twice daily and divalproex 2500 mg daily, and he had been seizure-free for three years.

On examination, he was lethargic but alert and fully oriented, with dysarthria and ataxia but no focal weakness. Vital signs were stable: blood pressure 123/59 mmHg, heart

rate 73 beats per minute, respiratory rate 16 breaths per minute, and oxygen saturation 94% on room air. Laboratory evaluation revealed serum sodium 140–142 mmol/L, potassium 2.9 mmol/L improving to 3.3 mmol/L after repletion, creatinine 1.0 mg/dL, aspartate aminotransferase 54 U/L, alanine aminotransferase 44 U/L, and white blood cell count 3.8–5.3 $\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$. His CBZ level was markedly elevated at 19.8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, while valproic acid levels were subtherapeutic (32–55 $\mu\text{g/mL}$).

Non-contrast CT of the head showed no acute abnormality but chronic bilateral basal ganglia calcifications and postsurgical changes. CT angiography of the head and neck showed no large vessel occlusion, stenosis, or dissection. A stroke alert was activated, but imaging was negative. The close temporal relationship between Paxlovid initiation and CBZ elevation supported a diagnosis of acute carbamazepine toxicity due to ritonavir interaction.

Carbamazepine, divalproex, and Paxlovid were discontinued, and the patient received supportive care, including intravenous fluids and electrolyte correction. Poison Control was consulted and recommended continued supportive therapy. His symptoms improved within 48 hours as CBZ levels declined, and he was discharged with neurology follow-up to transition to an alternative antiseizure medication.

Discussion

CBZ is metabolized predominantly by CYP3A4, making it particularly susceptible to interactions with strong CYP3A4 inhibitors such as ritonavir (1,2). Ritonavir causes irreversible inhibition of CYP3A4, resulting in rapid elevation of CBZ concentrations and subsequent neurotoxicity. Clinical manifestations frequently include dizziness, diplopia, ataxia, dysarthria, nystagmus, and

somnolence; in severe cases, seizures, coma, and respiratory compromise may develop.

Historical reports have repeatedly documented severe CBZ toxicity following the initiation of ritonavir or ritonavir-boosted antiretroviral therapy (4–8). (Table 1). In one notable case, even after ritonavir was discontinued and replaced with nelfinavir, CBZ levels decreased only partially—approximately 50%—demonstrating that nelfinavir also contributes to sustained inhibition of CBZ metabolism (7). These findings highlight the complexity of dosing adjustments when multiple protease inhibitors are involved.

With Paxlovid, this interaction remains clinically significant despite its short 5-day treatment duration. Ritonavir increases CBZ exposure, while CBZ induces CYP3A4 and may reduce nirmatrelvir concentrations, risking treatment failure (2,9). Therefore, Paxlovid is contraindicated in patients taking CBZ, and alternative COVID-19 therapies (e.g., remdesivir or molnupiravir) should be selected.

Management of CBZ toxicity is largely supportive. Airway protection, fluid resuscitation, and serial CBZ level monitoring are essential. In severe or refractory cases, extracorporeal treatments such as hemodialysis or hemoperfusion may be used due to CBZ's moderate dialyzability (3).

Conclusion

This case illustrates acute carbamazepine toxicity precipitated by the initiation of Paxlovid, presenting as a stroke mimic. Clinicians must avoid coadministration of CBZ with ritonavir-containing medications, conduct thorough medication reconciliation before prescribing Paxlovid, and monitor antiseizure medication levels whenever interactions are suspected.

Table 1. Prior Case Studies on Ritonavir–Carbamazepine Interactions

Author/Year	Protease Inhibitor(s)	Presentation	Outcome
Kato et al., 2000	Ritonavir	Vomiting, vertigo, transient liver	Resolved after stopping ritonavir & lowering CBZ
García et al., 2000	Ritonavir + CBZ (+phenytoin)	CBZ toxicity (ataxia, lethargy)	Improved after discontinuing CBZ
Burman & Orr, 2000	Ritonavir + Efavirenz	Worsening ataxia and falls	Improved after stopping CBZ and later restarting at lower
Mateu-de Antonio, 2001	Ritonavir switched to nelfinavir	Vertigo, drowsiness, disorientation,	Resolved after stopping ritonavir; partial
Bates & Herman, 2006	Lopinavir/ritonavir and nelfinavir	Excessive drowsiness, unsteady gait	Resolved after decreasing CBZ dose

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